

REHOUSE Objectives

The focus of the REHOUSE project is to increase the scope and productivity of the renovation process, the improvement of comfort and satisfaction of the building inhabitants and users, and the increased use of integrated solutions for the decentralised generation of renewable energy.

Eight renovation packages will be deployed across four EU demo sites. The goal of the project is to make the renovation packages market-ready by demonstrating them across a variety of environments. By the end of the project the renovation packages will have a technology-readiness-level of seven or more.

REHOUSE renovation principles

- Prefabrication and industrialisation of construction works
- Integration of onsite RES
- Smart management of energy transfers
- Multi-functionality of building envelope solutions
- Use of recycled and/or bio-sourced materials
- Affordable renovation solutions

Pictures show buildings before the renovation

Renovation solutions will be deployed across four demo sites

REHOUSE

Multi-source Heat Pump

Demo site
GR

The Multi-source Heat Pump is a smart, scalable heating and cooling solution using air, geothermal water and solar energy. It switches or combines sources via intelligent controls and local heat storage to maximise efficiency, reliability and peak-load reduction. Compared to single-source systems, it delivers higher seasonal performance, redundancy, and COPs up to 4.5 using low-GWP refrigerants. Suitable for new and renovated buildings, including cold climates.

Adaptable/dynamic building envelope

Reimagine building renovation with the Adaptable/Dynamic Building Envelope (ADBE). This smart façade system installs fast, adapts to any geometry, and boosts sustainability with integrated energy and air quality features, withstands major disruptive events, such as weather, fire and earthquakes. Made from recyclable materials, ADBE is a flexible solution built to perform, protect, and future-proof your building.

Demo site
GR, HU

SmartWall

Demo site
GR

The SmartWall enables renovation with a sleek, prefabricated and modular system that delivers heating, cooling, and ventilation - all in one. Designed for nZEB standards, it installs in plug-and-play design, adapts to any façade, and enhances comfort with smart features. Made from recyclable materials, SmartWall is the future of efficient, climate-ready buildings, suitable for diverse European climates.

Centralised Holistic H&C Renovation Kit

The Centralised Holistic Heating and Cooling Renovation Kit offers an all-in-one solution for building upgrades. It features a reversible water-to-water heat pump powered by onsite BIPV, bio-based PCM thermal energy storage, and smart controls using Model Predictive Control and Machine Learning. Easy-to-install sensors and open-source monitoring ensure efficient, sustainable performance.

Demo site
IT

Renovation Packages

Multipurpose façade with bio-based insulation and BIPV

Demo site
IT

This prefabricated Multipurpose Façade System combines eco-friendly hemp-based insulation with aesthetic BIPV panels to boost energy efficiency and thermal and acoustic comfort. Its stratified panel design with variable density ensures effective coupling with standard fixing systems, durability and easy installation, while meeting diverse architectural and energy standards for cost-effective, sustainable renovations.

PanoRen

Demo site
FR

PanoRen is a multifunctional façade system for sustainable renovations, built on the hybrid Panobloc® panel compatible with other building materials like concrete and metal. It integrates second-life PV slabs, RES production, embedded ventilation ducts, and recycled and bio-sourced materials. Prefabricated, it adapts to diverse geometries while boosting energy performance and installation efficiency.

Activated cellulose thermal insulation

Demo site
HU

This Activated Cellulose Thermal Insulation solution is made entirely from sawdust, free of chemicals or adhesives. It offers strong thermal performance, high compression strength, and recyclability. Designed for integration in renovation systems, it supports circular economy goals while enhancing building sustainability. This is one of the most sustainable thermal insulation material made of natural based materials with unrestricted recyclability.

Intelligent window system

The Intelligent Window System is a modular add-on that upgrades existing windows to reduce heat loss and improve energy efficiency. Smart sensors and microcontrollers adjust insulation based on solar input and demand, cutting winter heat loss by up to 50%. Prefabricated and low-cost, it minimizes tenant disruption. The IWS can be integrated into multi-purpose envelope solutions, such as the ADBE system, contributing to overall energy efficiency and sustainability in building renovations.

Demo site
HU

Demo sites

French demo site: Saint-Dié-des-Vosges
The demo-building is located along a roadside with rear parking and is surrounded by similar buildings and houses. The project focuses on improving insulation, airtightness, ventilation, and solar energy use, while optimizing façade installation methods and exploring replicability for future renovations.

Greek demo site: Kimmeria, Xanthi
The demo site is located on the Democritus University of Thrace campus in Kimmeria, near Xanthi. The focus is on improving energy efficiency, familiarizing users with innovative technologies, and engaging the local community in energy awareness and democratization efforts.

Hungarian demo site: Budapest
The demo site is a student-focused building in Budapest's 10th district, a formerly industrial area now undergoing renewal. The aim is to create an energy-efficient, welcoming living space for young people, reduce ecological impact and costs, support disadvantaged students, and showcase innovative technologies.

Italian demo site: Margherita di Savoia
The building is located in Margherita di Savoia, a coastal town in Apulia, Italy, known for its rich biodiversity and the historic Salt Pans. The building is currently inhabited, by about 20 people. The aim is to improve the building energy efficiency, comfort and social conditions through innovative technological interventions and solutions.

Partners

The REHOUSE project is coordinated by CARTIF and builds on the expertise of 25 partners from eight countries, leveraging a vast amount of knowledge and expertise to accelerate the European renovation wave.

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REHOUSE

ACCELERATING THE EUROPEAN RENOVATION RATE

Renovation packagEs for HOlistic improvement of EU's bUILDingS Efficiency, maximizing RESgeneration and cost-effectiveness

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